

Massive Open Online Course
THE POWER OF GENOMICS TO UNDERSTAND THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

About the course

The world was devastated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Genomics is key to understanding and responding to the disease. This course, the first of a series of five, introduces key concepts in viral genomics and how they can be applied to the current pandemic. It explores lessons that can be applied to future pandemic preparedness.

Learning outcomes

- Describe how viruses cause diseases and pandemics
- Discuss the use of sequence data for detecting and tracking the SARS-CoV-2 virus and its variants
- Describe the development and action of vaccines and therapeutics against SARS-CoV-2
- Evaluate the role of genomic epidemiology in pandemic decision-making
- Explain how data sharing contributes to developing effective strategies against the pandemic

Target audience

This course is designed for anyone interested in learning more about the genomics response to the current pandemic. While no prior knowledge about COVID-19 is required, it is likely to be most useful to researchers, healthcare professionals, science journalists, policymakers, and those working in public health.

Material repository website

https://wcscourses.github.io/COG-Train_Resources/power_of_genomics_home.html

Content

Week 1 - Pandemic and their origins

Glossary

Hypotheses of where COVID-19 came from

What is a Virus?

The SARS-CoV-2 virus

What is the difference between pandemic, epidemic, and outbreak?

Transmission of respiratory viruses

Genomic technologies for tracking COVID-19

The Great Influenza Pandemic of 1918

DNA, RNA and PCR

What is Genome Sequencing?

Tracking and reacting to outbreaks with genomic knowledge

How is SARS-CoV-2 sequencing done?

Week 2 - Viruses, Variants and Vaccines

What came before? Comparison with other coronaviruses (MERS/SARS)

The disappearance of SARS

The mechanism of viral replication

The Coronavirus Spike Protein

What is a vaccine?

Some vaccine approaches used for COVID-19

Up next - sequencing for vaccine development

The importance of sequencing in vaccine trials

How has genomics guided therapeutic design?

Variants Explained: Mutation, Variant, VOC

Tracking across a nation

SARS-CoV-2 Variants

Variants arising all over the world

Week 3 - Epidemiology and tracking in a pandemic

How to tackle a respiratory virus?

Introduction to Phylogenetics

Surveillance around the world

Identifying transmission clusters: Hospital outbreak investigation in the United Kingdom

Surveillance of viruses in a population

Genomic surveillance and its impacts

Sequencing surveillance options

What can we do better for the pandemics that may come?

Resources

Collaborators

Educators

Leigh Jackson, University of Exeter, United Kingdom

Sophie Prosolek, United Kingdom

Stephanie Hutchings, Bristol Health Security Agency (UKHSA), United Kingdom

Teresa Cutiño-Moguel, Royal College of Pathology, Barts Health, United Kingdom

Education developers

Jorge Batista da Rocha, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom

Liã Bárbara Arruda, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom

Contributors

Carlo Lapid, Philippine Genomics Center, Philippines
Carolina Torres, Argentine SARS-CoV-2 Genomics Consortium (PAIS Project), University of Buenos Aires, Argentina
Charlotte Williams, UCL Genomics, University College London, United Kingdom
Gerald Mboowa, Africa Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, Ethiopia
Mariana Viegas, Argentine SARS-CoV-2 Genomics Consortium (PAIS Project), Argentinean Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET), Argentina
Paola Niola, University College London, United Kingdom
Rachel Williams, UCL Genomics, University College London, United Kingdom
Sandra Cantinela, University College London, United Kingdom
Sunando Roy, University College London, United Kingdom
Stephen Bridgett, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom
Tapfumane Mashe, Ministry of Health and Child Care, Zimbabwe
Thanat Chookajorn, COVID-19 Network Investigations Alliance, Genomics and Evolutionary Medicine Unit, Mahidol University, Thailand

Reviewers

Camila Romano, Hospital das Clínicas, School of Medicine, University of São Paulo, Brazil
Charles Masembe, Makerere University, Uganda
Varun Shamanna, Central Research Laboratory, Kempegowda Institute of Medical Sciences, India

COG-UK contributors

Sharon Peacock, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
Alistair Darby, University of Liverpool, United Kingdom
Catherine Ludden, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
Darren Smith, Northumbria University, United Kingdom
Anna Markov, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
Peter McEwan, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom

Wellcome Connecting Science contributors

Treasa Creavin, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom
Alice Matimba, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom
Rachel Berkson, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom
Mel Sharpe, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom
Dusanka Nikolic, Wellcome Connecting Science, United Kingdom

Original version

Original platform: FutureLearn

Original course page: <https://www.futurelearn.com/courses/genomics-covid-19/2>

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